
**"HOW TO IMPROVE RESTAURANT PRODUCTIVITY AND REDUCE
TURNOVER WITH QUALIFIED WORKERS IN UZBEKISTAN".**

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Scientific advisor: **Nurmatova Sitora.Sh.**

Position: Senior lecture of KIUT.

E-mail address: Sitora-nurmatova@mail.ru

Tel. number: +998977510731.

Authors of article:

Alisherova Begoyim

a student of Kimyo International University in Tashkent. Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

Kobilova Dilsuz

a student of Kimyo International University in Tashkent. Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

Abstract.

The restaurant industry pertains to the provision of catering services in various establishments such as restaurants, bars, and cafes. Uzbekistan is renowned for its delectable traditional cuisine, and it is imperative to promote its restaurants and support the growth of restaurateurs in the country. In terms of tax expectations, the government is actively implementing reforms to fully disclose Uzbekistan's economic and human potential by utilizing its competitive advantages. Sectors that can boost the country's economic development receive initial attention and support. With these insights, it is crucial to explore methods to enhance service quality and minimize employee turnover in Uzbekistan's restaurants and catering industry.

Keywords.

restaurant industry; catering services; traditional cuisine; service quality; employee turnover.

Introduction part

The origin of the term "restaurant" can be traced back to the Latin word *restaur*, which means to strengthen or restore. In 1765, a French culinary expert named Boulanger established a public catering establishment in Paris that served broth as its main dish. Boulanger referred to the broth as a restorative dish and advertised his establishment as a place where people with stomach problems could come to be restored. Over time, the words "restorate" and "restorantes" evolved into the modern-day terms "restaurant" and "restaurant". However, restaurants in their current form existed in China during the Tang Dynasty (618-906) prior to their

emergence in France. The restaurant industry is not just about providing food, but also encompasses various leisure activities. It is a part of the larger hospitality industry and must be adaptable to changes in the external environment in order to remain competitive. Flexibility and diversity are key factors in maintaining relevance in the market.

Timur Abdullaev¹⁷¹

A good restaurant is not only delicious food and an ashtray changed on time, it is an atmosphere that needs to be taken into account, how to choose the right staff uniform when the lights are dimmed, music. This is an aura. For me, the aura of a restaurant is the emotions of the guests occupied by the whole room.

Timur Musin¹⁷²

A restaurant is like a theater, like a good movie, it is man-made, and, like any work of art, it must have a style, character, philosophy, gastronomic thought. This is what makes it different from cafes and eateries. The restaurant is art! There are many places of public catering and restaurants in Uzbekistan, in Tashkent itself more than 470 restaurants in Tashkent with contact details and their location on the map of Tashkent are indicated in the catalog directory. There are the following types of enterprises in this area: a restaurant, a dining car, a bar, a cafe, a summer cafe, a cafeteria, a canteen, a teahouse, a buffet and a snack bar. There is no specific data available on the exact number of workers in the restaurant industry in Uzbekistan.

However, according to the International Labour Organization, the service sector, which includes restaurants and catering, is the largest employer in Uzbekistan, accounting for approximately 40% of total employment.

Timur Musin

What is happening with the restaurant business in Uzbekistan and in Tashkent in particular? Starting to remember what happened 20 years ago, I understand that the development of the restaurant business is significant. Today Tashkent is becoming a real gastronomic capital of Central Asia, like other "Babylons" of the world.

Timur Musin

However, especially in recent times, the city's restaurants are becoming "plastic", they lack depth, philosophy, thought. A restaurant is like a theater, like a

¹⁷¹ Timur Abdullaev-Chairman of the Committee for the Development of the Restaurant and Hotel Business of the Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Uzbekistan, founder of the Academy of Restaurant Business, head of the Uzbek-Czech business union.

¹⁷² Timur Musin- founder of the themed restaurant chain Caravan Group and chairman of the Association of Restaurateurs and Hoteliers of Uzbekistan.

good movie, it is man-made, and, like any work of art, it must have a style, character, philosophy, gastronomic thought. This is what makes it different from cafes and eateries. It is not normal when there are still not enough clubs and DJs, restaurants of Peruvian and French cuisine in a city of three million, we still do not have good Chinese, Spanish, Greek restaurants. But their experience is very necessary for all of us, especially the young ones – after all, chefs, bartenders, head waiters, waiters, sommeliers and so on are trained in applied skills. So we will be able to bring our Uzbek cuisine under the standards of haute cuisine!

Timur Abdullaev

The restaurant business has its own fashion trends. How quickly do global trends reach Uzbekistan? What is fashionable now with us? We have very popular steak houses, American, Italian restaurants, Japanese cuisine. A lot of coffee shops have been opening lately. In many of them you can taste a salad or a hot dish. But in my understanding, a classic coffee house is coffee, dessert and nothing more. We don't understand this yet.

Timur Abdullaev

By the way, in Moscow now Uzbek cuisine is one of the three most popular ones, which undoubtedly pleases me. In fact, we do not have many restaurants, more cafes, canteens, well, or the so-called Milliy Taomlar catering points. Given the characteristic feature of our mentality, it is important to find the right approach to the guest, I emphasize, to the guest, and not to the client. It is believed that the client pays, and the guest sits for free. **But hospitality is in our blood and every visitor is a guest for us.**

The pandemic has had a significant impact on the promotion of restaurants and tourism in Uzbekistan, resulting in a decrease in the number of tourists and revenue for the industry due to the closure of restaurants and cafes during the lockdown. The government's measures to control the spread of the virus, such as travel restrictions and quarantine requirements, have also made it difficult for tourists to visit the country, negatively affecting the promotion of restaurants and other tourist attractions. To adapt to the new normal, businesses have shifted their focus to online marketing and promotion using social media platforms and other digital channels. However, the pandemic has highlighted the need for more investment in digital infrastructure and technology in Uzbekistan's restaurant and tourism industries to better promote themselves online and reach a wider audience, even during times of crisis. The COVID-19 pandemic has caused a health crisis and a sharp decline in economic sustainability, particularly in tourism management, with consequences that are still difficult to measure in most countries.

This study aims to explore the views of restaurant owners on the future of their businesses, government actions taken during the pandemic, strategies they plan to implement, and lessons learned for the future. The findings indicate that there are shared concerns among restaurant entrepreneurs regarding the post-pandemic period, including the need for effective government measures, adaptation to markets with greater availability, building resilience for the future, and generating working capital. These concerns reflect the challenges faced by the restaurant industry in navigating the pandemic and preparing for the future.

The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the restaurant industry has been severe, leading to job losses and closures. Around 15% of all restaurants permanently closed within six months of the introduction of restrictive measures in March 2020. However, many restaurants adapted to the situation by offering delivery services, with about 90% planning to provide this service in the near future. Despite this change, restaurant turnover decreased by up to 70%. The pandemic also affected the hotel sector, with cancellations of room reservations increasing rapidly. The government's Tourism 2015 plan aimed to increase revenues from tourism and create employment opportunities in the industry. The COVID-19 pandemic has had a severe impact on the restaurant industry, resulting in closures and job losses. Within six months of restrictive measures being introduced in March 2020, approximately 15% of all restaurants closed permanently. Despite this, many restaurants adapted by offering delivery services, with about 90% planning to continue doing so in the future. However, restaurant turnover decreased by up to 70%. The hotel sector was also affected, with an increase in cancellations of room reservations. The government's Tourism 2015 plan aimed to boost tourism revenues and create employment opportunities in the industry. In the short term, the closure of restaurants and schools has had the most significant impact, as foodservice sales in Canada were valued at \$65.0 billion in 2017, compared to \$74.0 billion in retail sales. However, it is likely that total food consumption remains unchanged, as volumes lost from the foodservice channel are being picked up by retail. Suppliers are adapting by setting up packing lines and converting existing lines to cater to retail buyers. US data shows that by March 8, 2020, retail food sales had already increased by 10.6% overall and 4.5% for fresh produce as quarantine measures began in the most affected states.

The food industry has become a significant contributor to Uzbekistan's economy, making up 13% of its GDP. The number of registered food industry enterprises has increased from 8,050 in 2014-2015 to 12,065 in 2017-2018, while investments in fixed assets have grown from 102.0 million USD in 2015-2017 to

495.7 million USD in 2018, with a growth rate of 485%. This sector accounts for 6.4% of Uzbekistan's total exports and 9.8% of its total industrial investment. Additionally, it is the fourth largest FDI recipient in the country.

According to DP-3594, foreign-invested companies in Uzbekistan that specialize in producing goods or services are exempt from various taxes and contributions, including corporate income tax, property tax, single tax payments for micro and small businesses, and contributions to the Republican Road Fund.

Foreign-invested companies in Uzbekistan that specialize in producing goods or services are eligible for tax exemptions, including corporate income tax, property tax, single tax payments for micro and small businesses, and contributions to the Republican Road Fund, as per DP-3594. As a result, there has been an increase in foreign investment in the food industry, with companies like Nestle, Coca-Cola, and PepsiCo setting up operations in the country. The government has also taken steps to support the food industry's growth by establishing a Food Industry Development Fund and adopting a Food Industry Development Program for 2019-2021. Uzbekistan's agricultural resources, such as cotton, wheat, fruits, and vegetables, are utilized by the food industry to produce dairy products, meat, confectionery, and beverages. Overall, the food industry's expansion has created employment opportunities and contributed to the country's economic development. With continued government support and investment, the sector is expected to continue growing and bolstering the country's prosperity.

Main Part

In April 2022, an examination of the catering industry was conducted by the Ministry of Justice in which 2,100 representatives were surveyed. Additionally, various regulations, statistical data, and other sources were analyzed in order to identify obstacles to the growth of restaurants and tourism. The inquiry revealed six major challenges, ranging from outdated sanitary provisions to instances of corruption. The Ministry of Justice recommends amending legislation that is no longer up to date to tackle these concerns. The survey disclosed that public catering businesses encounter the following difficulties:

First, outdated legislation.

According to the report, restaurants are obliged to display a warning a week ahead of their closure for cleaning, maintenance, or other purposes or risk being fined 2 million soums. The catering industry's sanitary rules and regulations no longer conform to current standards. For instance, cooking on stoves utilizing coal, wood, or solid fuel is not permitted (this rule cannot be adhered to during winters

with limited gas supplies). Furthermore, knives must be separated for use on 12 distinct types of food, providing another example.

Secondly, the tax burden and complex tax administration.

The Ministry of Justice reports that public catering establishments must pay between 7 to 9 taxes, including turnover tax (if the turnover is below 1 billion soums), value-added tax, income tax, social tax, personal income tax (as a tax collector), property tax, land tax, tax for utilizing water resources, and a fee imposed on the sale of alcoholic products. As a result, approximately 1/3 of respondents have trouble comprehending the tax legislation in their daily operations. These challenges, in turn, contribute to a substantial shadow economy (30-40%) within the sector.

Thirdly, numerous inspections.

It has been revealed that public catering businesses are frequently disrupted by over 10 state entities, including tax, fire, sanitary, labor, law enforcement, and housing and communal services. The Ministry of Justice reports that from 2020-2021, approximately 8,000 inspections were conducted by three departments (tax, fire, and sanitary). This implies that on average, 14.5% of public catering establishments undergo an inspection every year. Nevertheless, enterprises who participated in the survey had a differing point of view, with 2.1 thousand respondents stating that as many as three inspections were conducted monthly, indicating that there are actually 5.5 thousand inspections each month, and some may even be unlawful.

Fourth, cases of corruption during inspections.

The regulations overseeing this sector are intricate, meaning that catering establishments may inadvertently breach them. These contraventions result in inspections, which have the potential to foster corrupt practices. As an illustration, 26.4% of individuals surveyed (905) acknowledged experiencing instances of corruption in the tax department, 20.3% (697) in the sanitary sector, and 11.3% (387) in fire safety regulatory agencies. The participants also highlighted that the most prevalent form of corruption is the proffering of free service by personnel affiliated with government institutions.

Fifth, problems with connection to engineering and communication networks and interruptions in the supply of gas, electricity and water.

A majority of the individuals interviewed who belonged to public catering establishments (63.4%) highlighted that they encountered difficulties related to accessing infrastructure facilities when commencing their operations.

Training employees is a commonly used strategy in fast-growing organizations. Its main objective is to improve the functionality and efficiency of the organization while also catering to management's needs for change management. Given the rapidly evolving professional skill requirements, continuous employee training has become a critical factor for any organization's success. In Russia, organizations greatly emphasize the educational and professional development of their future and current employees to help them meet the high demands of the market. With external and internal factors impacting an organization quickly, training personnel has become a key task, not only as an organizational goal, but also as an organizational development process. The preparation of a detailed curriculum depends on the educational tasks and personnel training goals. Moreover, it is essential to consider the individual characteristics of the employee being trained. The primary objective of employee training is to prepare them to undertake their tasks successfully. The employer's goals concerning professional staff development significantly differ from the employee's aspirations for growth and problem-solving abilities.

German specialists V. Bartz¹⁷³ and H. Scheibl¹⁷⁴ believe that the goals of continuous training for an employer are:

- organization and formation of management personnel;
- mastering the ability to define: understand and solve problems;
- personnel reproduction;
- staff integration;
- flexible staff formation;
- adaptation;
- introduction of innovations.

Experts suggest various methods for retaining top employees and organizing work efficiently in the restaurant industry, including:

1. Offering competitive pay and attractive benefits, such as health insurance, vacation days, and other perks to show employee appreciation.
2. Creating a positive workplace atmosphere through open communication, promoting growth opportunities, and encouraging teamwork.
3. Providing continuous training and education programs, including workshops, seminars, and online courses to improve employee skills and knowledge.

¹⁷³ V. Bartz - He was first a social democratic and then a communist politician.

¹⁷⁴ H. Scheibl - He is one of the most important Austrian representatives of abstract painting.

4. Recognizing and rewarding good performance, which can be as simple as a thank you or a small bonus.

5. Establishing a clear career path to keep employees motivated and engaged in the organization.

6. Encouraging feedback from employees to enhance the work experience and show that their opinion matters.

7. Offering flexible scheduling and paid time off to promote a healthy work-life balance.

8. Fostering an environment of respect and dignity, recognizing and dealing with any harassment or discrimination promptly.

The restaurant industry faces several potential risks, including production, commercial, financial, and those related to force majeure. Production risks often stem from interruptions to the production cycle, such as due to delays in the delivery of raw materials or goods. To mitigate these risks, it is important to implement the following measures:

- Establish control mechanisms over the production cycle in the restaurant.
- Monitor the quality of raw material and goods supplies.
- Enhance the payment methods and settlement procedures with suppliers.
- Regulate and monitor the shelf-life of raw material and goods stocks.

There are various commercial risks that can affect the restaurant business, including a decline in market size, reduced consumer demand, and the emergence of new competitors. To mitigate these risks, the following measures can be implemented:

- Regularly monitor and analyze restaurant market conditions.
- Improve pricing strategies and offer consumer discounts or loyalty programs.
- Develop a strong brand identity and reputation through targeted marketing efforts and public relations initiatives.
- Advertise the restaurant through various channels.

Monetary risks are linked to inflation, irregular payments, and changes in currency rates. Effective financial management can help lower these risks. When it comes to force majeure risks, they pertain to unpredictable and exceptional circumstances. To minimize these risks, it is crucial to establish a restaurant business with adequate financial stability.

Let's examine some risk mitigation examples:

1. The threat of premises loss due to expired lease agreements may be countered by potentially purchasing the property with profits.

2. If sales are inadequate, the following approaches may be implemented:

- modifying the discount system;
- creating a new, more cost-effective menu.

3. The possibility of falling short on projected earnings may necessitate setting aside money for unexpected costs, such as enhancing the entertainment program or attracting more customers.

4. The possibility of staff not meeting expected criteria.

To avoid this situation, the following steps are recommended:

- Recruit employees who possess relevant work experience.
- Hold regular training sessions and certify personnel.
- Offer a bonus in addition to their regular wage as a means of incentivizing good work.

TASHKENT, January 27 - Sputnik. In Tashkent, the Meal&Drinks Choice-2019 restaurant award was presented again, writes MyDay.uz. The purpose of the award is to celebrate the best establishments for the year and popularize the restaurant industry in Tashkent. For three months, people voted for their favorite places on the award. myday website.uz in 11 nominations. The first and second stages of the award were completed in December 2019, a total of 55 thousand votes were recorded. At this stage, the winners and finalists of the popular vote were determined.

Winners:

the best cafe:	the best fast food restaurant:	the best interior of a restaurant:	the best bar:	the best establishment of pan Asian cuisine:	the best establishment of European cuisine:	the best establishment of National cuisine:
Paul	Чебуречная №1	Nobile	The Bar	Hori	Nobile	Caravan
Breadly	Fish&Bread	Куранты	Sette Bar	HUMO	Куранты	Cafe Aksu
Чайкоф	Chopar Pizza	Голубые купола	Куранты	Teppanyaki	L'Opera	Rayhon

Also note the trend of 2019: club restaurants

Queens, 7 пятниц, GOSTY Restaurant.

The best restaurant: the choice of restaurateurs - Paul

The best chef - Laziz Gulyamov

Grand Prix "The best restaurant of the year" - Nobile

We have conducted an experiment that can be useful and informative.

Data obtained from the mobile survey for 2023:

Features that customer want in a restaurant app

Factors that make customers return to a restaurant

Conclusion:

To facilitate the assessment of industry-specific norms, it would be beneficial to use Dineserv to conduct regular surveys at both the national and local levels. This information would enable DiNESERV.per users to differentiate between shifts in service quality and changes in normative expectations.

Moreover, for restaurant owners seeking a competitive edge, it may prove valuable to survey customers of other establishments using DiNESERV.per. This measure can help enhance one's ability to succeed in a highly competitive market.

The perceived quality of service can be attributed to the interplay of three variables that operate independently: normative expectations, predictive expectations, and the actual quality of service received. When consumers have lower normative expectations about the expected level of service, their perception of the actual quality of service improves. Conversely, when consumers hold higher predictive expectations about what they anticipate will happen, their resulting perception of the actual quality of service also improves.

To enhance how customers perceive service, there exist three distinct methods:

- Enhancing the quality of service.
- Lowering the standards for what should occur during a service.
- Raising the expectations for what will happen during a service.

Marketing is instrumental in altering the expectations of customers.

What's the point?

It's crucial to prioritize improving the perception score because a higher score equals a greater likelihood that customers will return, as well as recommend your establishment to others. Conversely, around 91% of dissatisfied restaurant-goers won't give your business another chance, and they'll usually tell eight to ten people about their negative experiences.

When customers return, profits increase. According to Bill Marriott, it costs \$10 to bring a guest to a Marriott hotel for the first time, but only \$1 in special effort to entice them back. Additionally, as your relationships with customers strengthen over time, their contribution to your profits will grow substantially. If your establishment can swivel the percentage of customers who plan to return from 76% to 81%, your restaurant's net profit is liable to double.

How much does word-of-mouth advertising matter? A Gallup report illustrated that of the people heading to a restaurant for the first time, 44% did so based on a recommendation, and another 10% ventured there with someone who had already gone.

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